

The effect of inhibitor structure on the corrosion of copper in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution

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Manuscript received online 30 March 2015, accepted 15 October 2016

Abstract : The inhibition effect of glycine (1), aspartic acid (3) and their various derivatives namely *N*-benzenesulphonyl glycine (2), *N*-benzenesulphonyl aspartic acid (4), α -benzenesulphonamido- β -2-benzimidazolyl-propionic acid (5), 1-benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis(2-benzimidazolyl)ethane (6), α -benzenesulphonamido- β -2-(1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidinyl) propionic acid (7), 1-benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis-2-(1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidinyl) ethane (8), α -benzenesulphonamido- β -(2-imidazolynyl)propionic acid (9) and 1-benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis(2-imidazolynyl)ethane (10) against the corrosion of copper in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution (pH 6) have been studied using weight loss and potentiodynamic polarization methods. The inhibition efficiency of these compounds increases in the order : 1 < 2 < 3 < 4 < 5 < 6 < 7 < 8 < 9 < 10. Compounds having zwitter ion structure under the experimental condition are found to be less effective. Imidazoline derivatives are found to be better corrosion inhibitor for copper. The adsorption of the inhibitors follows Langmuir isotherm. The adsorption free energy indicates chemisorptions of the inhibitors on the metal surface.

Keywords : Glycine, aspartic acid, corrosion inhibition, polarisation, benzimidazole, imidazoline, tetrahydropyrimidine, chemisorption.

Introduction

Copper and its alloys find extensive application as water piping valves, heat exchange tube and tube sheets, shafts, roofing and bearings etc. It exhibits good corrosion resistance to urban, marine and industrial atmospheres. However in the presence of oxygen, chloride, sulphate and nitrate ions, it is exposed to localized attack¹. Thus, corrosion of copper and its inhibition in a wide variety of media, particularly when they contain chloride ions, have attracted the attention of many investigators. One current approach to protect metals and alloys against corrosion is the use of inhibitors. Amongst them there are inorganic inhibitors. Manganate-- MnO_4^- , chromate-- CrO_4^{2-} , molybdate-- MoO_4^{2-} , tetraborate-- $\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and phosphate-- PO_4^{3-} are useful². But large number of organic compounds such as azoles, amines, Schiff bases, imidazolines, hydroxyrimidines, amino acids etc. are useful corrosion inhibitors in acidic³⁻⁹, neutral¹⁰⁻¹² and alkaline media¹³. Depending on the structure, they

act as a protective layer formed by physisorption in the metal/electrolyte interphase or as an insoluble chelate barrier developed by chemisorptions which avoid direct contact of the metal/alloy with the aggressive media¹⁴.

Due to restrictive inhibitor laws, inorganic corrosion inhibitors such as chromate or nitrites are replaced by organic compounds¹⁵. Benzotriazole and its derivatives offer a good protection against corrosion of brass in aggressive environments, viz. 3–3.5% NaCl solutions and sea water¹⁶. But these compounds are toxic¹¹. Amino acids and their derivatives are of particular importance as corrosion inhibitors because they are environmentally friendly and have very low toxicity^{6,17}.

Recently extensive work is going on the inhibition effect of various amino acids on copper and steel in HCl, HNO_3 and H_2SO_4 media. In order to introduce non-toxic organic inhibitor for copper in acidic chloride solution, cysteine was used by Ismail⁶. Inhibition efficiency was 84%. Presence of Cu^{2+} ion increases the inhibition effi-

ciency to 90%. Glycine, alanine, tyrosine are also found to be good corrosion inhibitors in acidic media¹⁸. Sulphonamides are of considerable importance for their physiological activity and behave as good microbial corrosion inhibitor for mild steel¹⁹ in salty water environment. Looking for environmentally acceptable corrosion inhibitors for copper in marine environment, we have chosen amino acids viz. glycine (**1**) and aspartic acid (**3**) as starting materials and *N*-benzenesulphonyl glycine (**2**) and *N*-benzenesulphonyl aspartic acid (**4**) have been prepared. These molecules contain O, N and S atoms and may function as good corrosion inhibitors for copper in chloride solution. The carboxylic group has been converted to benzimidazole, imidazoline or hydroxyrimidine group in stepwise manner to improve further their inhibition activity and α -benzenesulphonamido- β -2-benzimidazolyl-propionic acid (**5**), 1-benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis(2-benzimidazolyl)ethane (**6**), α -benzenesulphonamido- β -2-(1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidinyl) propionic acid (**7**), 1-benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis-2-(1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidinyl) ethane (**8**), α -benzenesulphonamido- β -(2-imidazolynyl)propionic acid (**9**) and 1-benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis(2-imidazolynyl)ethane (**10**) have been synthesized. These compounds may act as polydentate chelating agents and expected to be good inhibitors for copper in chloride solution due to the presence of O, N and S atoms, basic benzimidazole, imidazoline or hydroxyrimidine moiety and π electron effect of the benzene ring and a number of adsorption sites. Potentiodynamic polarization (PP) technique has been used to study the effect of the addition of these compounds on the corrosion of copper in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution. The aim of this study is to synthesize environment friendly corrosion inhibitors for copper. As the comparative consideration of the inhibitors is important in this investigation, proper attention is paid too obtain reliable data concerning their inhibiting properties.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

The chemical composition of copper used in the present study was 98.46% Cu, 1.26% Zn, 0.24% Fe and traces

of Pb, Sn, Ni, P and Mn. The working electrode for potentiodynamic study was prepared from the copper rod and only the circular cross-section (0.25 cm²) of rod was exposed. The copper sample was polished successively with belt grinding polishing machine, metallographic emery paper of increasing fineness of up to 1200 grade and cloth polishing by single disc polishing machine CENSICO PMV-T 10-1. Then the samples were degreased with AR grade ethanol and acetone and rinsed with double distilled water prior to each experiment.

Amino acids were AR grade reagents and used as received. The compounds **2** and **4** were prepared by following usual procedure. Benzimidazole derivatives (**5** and **6**) were prepared by refluxing compound **4** (0.1 mole) and *o*-phenylene diamine (0.2 mole) in 60 ml 4 N HCl solution for 4 h²⁰. Imidazoline derivatives (**9** and **10**) were prepared by heating a mixture of compound **4** and ethylene diamine in 1 : 2 mole ratio at 130–160 °C for 8 h in air atmosphere²¹. Hydroxyrimidine derivatives (**7** and **8**) were prepared following similar procedure using propylene diamine in place of ethylene diamine²². Analytical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

The pH measurements were made with an Orion 420A Plus pH meter using 9157BN Triode pH electrode. The pH meter was calibrated with sodium hydrogen phthalate and borax buffer solution in water. Following solutions (50 mL) were titrated potentiometrically in water-methanol (1 : 1) at 30 \pm 0.5 °C and ionic strength 0.25 (NaClO₄) against 0.150 M NaOH solution : (i) 0.01 M HClO₄, (ii) 0.01 M HClO₄ + 0.02 M 2 or 4 or 5H⁺ or 6H₂²⁺ or 7H⁺ or 8H₂²⁺ or 9H⁺ or 10H₂²⁺ and (iii) 0.01 M HClO₄ + 0.03 M 2 or 4 or 5H⁺ or 6H₂²⁺ or 7H⁺ or 8H₂²⁺ or 9H⁺ or 10H₂²⁺. The ligand perchlorates were obtained *in situ* by mixing quantitatively **5** or **6** or **7** or **8** or **9** or **10** and HClO₄ in appropriate molar ratio. The aggressive environment used was 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution prepared from AR grade reagent and double distilled water. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6.0. Oxygen content of the sodium chloride solution was 7.3 mg/L. All other reagents were of AR quality.

Table 1. Analytical data of the inhibitors

Inhibitor	Percentage yield	Melting points (°C)	Observed (Calcd.) (%)			pK ^a value	
			C	H	N	pK ₁ ^a	pK ₂ ^a
4	50	170	–	–	5.30 (5.12)	5.34 (COOH) 3.75 (COOH)	
5^a	40	226	52.30 (52.89)	4.80 (4.68)	11.60 (11.57)	5.53 (Benzimidazolium ion) 3.39 (COOH)	
6	30	200	62.98 (63.31)	4.75 (4.56)	16.59 (16.79)	4.69 (Benzimidazolium ion) 2.92 (COOH)	
7	9	152	50.25 (50.16)	5.95 (6.10)	13.25 (13.50)	10.50 (Hydropyrimidinium ion) 2.15 (COOH)	
8	3.7	148	53.50 (53.73)	6.15 (6.27)	21.05 (20.89)	10.40 (Hydropyrimidinium ion) 3.10 (Hydropyrimidinium ion)	
9	10	208	48.46 (48.48)	5.00 (5.05)	13.99 (14.14)	10.30 (Imidazolium ion) 2.92 (COOH)	
10	12	230	52.30 (52.33)	5.90 (5.91)	21.65 (21.80)	10.25 (Imidazolium ion) 3.10 (Imidazolium ion)	

^aContain one water molecule.*Potentiodynamic polarization study :*

The potentiodynamic polarization studies were carried out with polished and degreased copper specimens having an exposed surface area of 0.25 cm². The electrochemical measurements were carried out in a standard three-electrode electrochemical cell of volume 100 mL. The counter electrode was a platinum plate with 1 cm² surface area, the reference electrode consisted of a commercial saturated calomel electrode with a Luggin capillary bridge and the working electrode was made up of copper. Polarization studies were carried out using potentiostat/galvanostat (ACM Instruments Gill AC) and the data obtained were analyzed using the software ACM Instruments version 5 in air atmosphere. The degreased working electrode was immersed in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution and allowed to stabilize for 30 min²³. The cathodic and anodic polarization curves of brass specimen in the test solution with and without inhibitors were recorded at a scan rate of 1 mV/s in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution (pH 6) at 30 ± 0.5 °C. The inhibition efficiencies of the compounds were determined from corrosion current density using the Tafel extrapolation method.

Weight loss method :

Weight loss measurements were carried out using cop-

per specimens of size (2.5×2.5×0.3 cm). These were immersed in 100 mL 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution (pH 6) without inhibitor and in the presence of 10⁻⁵–10⁻⁶ M inhibitor concentration for 6 days at 30±0.5 °C in air atmosphere. Mettler Toledo Model No. AL54 balance was used for determining the weight.

Results and discussion

The ability of an organic molecule to inhibit metal corrosion depends on several factors and some of them are the shape, aromaticity, bond strength to metal substrate, the presence of heteroatom and number of bonding atoms or groups²⁴. Temperature, pH and stability in the aggressive media are also factors related to the efficiency of the inhibitor²⁵. All compounds are stable in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution. Room temperature 30±0.5 °C was selected for inhibition studies. Concentration of chloride ion in sea water is 0.54 M. Hence 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution is chosen glycine is good inhibitor in HCl and H₂SO₄ solution²⁶ where it exists as protonated species. But at pH 6 inhibition efficiency of glycine on corrosion of copper in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution is found to be only 10.1%. This may be due to zwitter ion structure of glycine (**1**).

Cysteine was found to be better corrosion inhibitor for copper in acidic medium where it exists as protonated species than in neutral medium where it exists as zwitter ion⁶. After introducing C₆H₅SO₂- group, inhibition efficiency is increased by 10.8% (**2**).

This is due to the absence of zwitter ion structure of the inhibitor, pi-electron of the benzene ring and introduction of electron rich group -SO₂- group in the derivative (**3**). Aspartic acid contains more coordination site and as expected its inhibition efficiency is greater than glycine.

After introducing C₆H₅SO₂- group, inhibition efficiency is increased by 11.8% as in the case of glycine.

Aspartic acid is a polydentate chelating agent. Two carboxylic groups have been converted in stepwise manner to basic benzimidazole, imidazoline or hydroxypyrimidine group to improve further their inhibition activity and synthesized α -benzenesulphonamido- β -2-benzimidazolyl-propionic acid (**5**), 1-benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis(2-benzimidazolyl)ethane (**6**), α -benzenesulphonamido- β -2-(1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidinyl) propionic acid (**7**), 1-

benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis-2-(1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidinyl) ethane (**8**), α -benzenesulphonamido- β -(2-imidazolynyl)propionic acid (**9**) and 1-benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis(2-imidazolynyl)ethane (**10**).

The condensation of (**4**) with *o*-phenylene diamine, ethylene diamine or propylene diamine produces six compounds (Fig. 1). Analytical data are stated in Tables 1 and 2. All the mono compounds (**5**, **7** and **9**) exist as zwitter ion supported by IR data. Compound (**4**) shows a strong band at 1705 cm⁻¹ due to -COOH group which is absent in the IR spectra of **5**, **7** and **9**. In addition COO⁻ asymmetrical and symmetrical stretching bands are observed at 1580 cm⁻¹ and 1360 cm⁻¹ (**5**); 1657 cm⁻¹ and 1416 cm⁻¹ (**7**) and 1663 cm⁻¹ and 1390 cm⁻¹ (**9**) respectively. The yield of imidazoline and hydroxypyrimidine derivatives is low. But yield may be improved by heating the reaction mixture in the presence of benzene. As the benzene distilled, water formed from the reaction mixture may be removed as an azeotropic mixture and the yield may be improved²⁷. The scheme of synthesis of the inhibitors is given in Fig. 2.

Table 2. The IR frequencies (cm⁻¹) of interest with tentative assignments

Compounds	C-H and N-H stretches	C=N stretches	SO ₂ -N < Band II and I	COO ⁻ stretches asymmetrical symmetrical
4	3260m		1330m	1705s
	3150w		1155s	due to -COOH
5^a	3380m	1620s	1310s	1580
	3060m		1150s	1360s
	2990m, 2850m			
6	2950s	1600w	1372m	
	2920s		1152m	
	2855s			
7	3352s	1581b	1331s	1663sh
	3258s		1161s	1390sh
	2925w			
8	3353s	1562s	1334s	
	3260s		1162s	
9	3350s	1561s	1332s	1657sh
	3265s		1163s	1416sh
10	3352s	1562m,b	1333s	
	3264s		1162s	

^aContain one water molecule.

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Structure of the compounds	Inhibition efficiency (%)
$\text{H}_2\text{N}-\overset{\text{H}}{\underset{\text{O}}{\text{C}}}-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{C}}-\text{H}$ <p>Glycine (1)</p>	10.1
<p><i>N</i>-Benzenesulphonyl glycine (2)</p>	20.9
<p>Aspartic acid (3)</p>	26.7
<p><i>N</i>-Benzenesulphonyl aspartic acid (4)</p>	38.5
<p>α-Benzenesulphonamido-β-2-benzimidazolyl propionic acid (5)</p>	59.5
<p>1-Benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis(2-benzimidazolyl)ethane (6)</p>	77.0
<p>α-Benzenesulphonamido-β-2-(1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidinyl)propionic acid (7)</p>	77.8

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of the inhibitors and their inhibition efficiency.

Potentiodynamic polarization study :

At chloride concentrations lower than 1 M, the mechanism of copper dissolution can be expressed as :

Higher cuprous complexes such as CuCl_3^{2-} and CuCl_4^{3-} are formed when $[\text{Cl}^-] > 1 \text{ M}$ ²⁸. The cathodic reaction consists of reduction of oxygen :

The representative cathodic and anodic polarization curves of copper in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution with varying concentrations (10^{-4} M to 10^{-6} M) of inhibitor **1** are shown in the Fig. 3. The potentiodynamic polarization parameters are listed in Table 3. Inhibition efficiencies²⁹ are calculated using the following equation,

$$\text{Inhibition efficiency} = \frac{[I_{\text{corr}} - I_{\text{corr}(\text{inh})}]/I_{\text{corr}}}{I_{\text{corr}}} \times 100$$

where $I_{\text{corr}(\text{inh})}$ and I_{corr} are the corrosion current density value with and without inhibitor, respectively.

All reagents show relatively same behaviour against the polarization. Moreover, these inhibitors do not change the profile of the anodic and cathodic curves, indicating that the inhibitors merely block the reaction sites of metal surface without affecting the anodic and cathodic reaction mechanism. The inhibitor molecules produce a chemisorbed layer on copper surface which the chloride ion can not penetrate easily³⁰. With increasing inhibitor concentration, no obvious trend is observed in the shift of E_{corr} values, suggesting that these compounds behave as mixed-type inhibitors⁵.

The carboxyl group of (**4**) is converted to benzimidazole group in stepwise manner and the inhibition efficiency of mono benzimidazole derivative (**5**) is more than (**4**) due to the presence of more nitrogen atoms and more basic character of (**5**).

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The inhibition efficiency is further improved (77.0%) by converting the remaining -COOH group of (5) to benzimidazole group. This is due to the presence of more nitrogen atoms, benzimidazole groups and absence of zwitter ion structure. When the benzimidazole group is replaced by more basic imidazoline group, the inhibition efficiency is further improved (87.0%).

The inhibition efficiency of (4) is also improved when the carboxylic group is converted to tetrahydropyrimidine group in stepwise manner (7 and 8). Though more basic

than the imidazoline derivatives, tetrahydropyrimidine derivatives exhibit less inhibition efficiency. This may be due to steric effect²². The inhibition efficiency order is found to be $1 < 2 < 3 < 4 < 5 < 6 < 7 < 8 < 9 < 10$ by weight loss as well as potentiodynamic polarization method.

Adsorption isotherm :

The inhibitors exhibit various inhibition efficiencies due to their different adsorption abilities (physical adsorption or chemisorption on copper surface). Now for

Fig. 2. Scheme of synthesis of the inhibitors.

getting more information about the specific interactions between inhibitors and copper surface different adsorption isotherms were tested and we got best fitted linear relationship in Langmuir isotherm^{5,6} :

$$\text{Langmuir isotherm : } C_{\text{inh}}/\theta = C_{\text{inh}} + 1/K_{\text{ads}}$$

where K_{ads} is the equilibrium constant for adsorption process, C_{inh} is the concentration of inhibitor and θ is the surface coverage, which is calculated from the polarization data using following equation :

$$\theta = (i_{\text{corr}} - i_{\text{corr(inh)}})/i_{\text{corr}}$$

where, i_{corr} and $i_{\text{corr(inh)}}$ are the corrosion current densities in the absence and in the presence of inhibitors, respectively.

From the C_{inh}/θ against C_{inh} plots (representative Fig. 4) we can get K_{ads} and R^2 values which are given in Table 4. The higher K_{ads} values (i.e. $\geq 100 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$), indicate that a stronger and more stable adsorbed layer has been formed, which increases the inhibition efficiency³¹ and $R^2 > 0.99$ indicates that adsorption follows the Langmuir adsorption isotherm³². Now the adsorption equilibrium constant, $K_{\text{ads}}^{\text{values}}$ obtain from the Langmuir adsorption isotherm is related to the standard free energy of adsorption ($\Delta G^{\circ}_{\text{ads}}$) :

$$\Delta G^{\circ}_{\text{ads}} = -2.303 RT \log (55.5 K_{\text{ads}})$$

where R is the universal gas constant, T is the temperature and the value of 55.5 is the molar concentration of

Table 3. The electrochemical parameters and inhibition efficiency values for the corrosion of copper in 0.6 M NaCl solution

Inhibitor	Concentration (M)	E_{corr} (mV) vs SCE	I_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	I.E. (%)
Blank	–	–289.2	5.08	–
1	10^{-4}	–280.0	4.67	8.1
	10^{-5}	–252.3	4.57	10.0
	10^{-6}	–259.4	4.80	5.4
2	10^{-4}	–273.0	4.18	17.6
	10^{-5}	–261.1	4.02	20.9
	10^{-6}	–268.7	4.22	16.8
3	10^{-4}	–240.9	4.37	14.0
	10^{-5}	–246.9	3.72	26.7
	10^{-6}	–258.7	4.44	12.6
4	10^{-4}	–223.5	3.40	33.1
	10^{-5}	–242.5	3.12	38.4
	10^{-6}	–238.1	3.52	30.7
5	10^{-4}	–224.2	2.26	55.5
	10^{-5}	–212.5	2.06	59.5
	10^{-6}	–264.5	2.47	51.3
6	10^{-4}	–263.7	2.06	59.4
	10^{-5}	–248.5	1.52	69.9
	10^{-6}	–237.3	1.16	77.0
7	10^{-4}	–273.4	1.68	66.8
	10^{-5}	–206.6	1.12	77.8
	10^{-6}	–221.2	1.25	75.2
8	10^{-4}	–277.4	4.50	11.3
	10^{-5}	–224.9	0.94	81.5
	10^{-6}	–238.0	1.06	79.0
9	10^{-4}	–259.8	3.42	32.5
	10^{-5}	–238.3	0.97	80.9
	10^{-6}	–230.2	0.81	84.0
10	10^{-4}	–261	1.26	75.1
	10^{-5}	–245.4	0.91	82.0
	10^{-6}	–226.7	0.66	87.0
	10^{-6}	–242.3	1.08	78.7

water in the solution. Various ΔG°_{ads} values are given in Table 4. The negative ΔG°_{ads} values are consistent with the condition for spontaneity of the adsorption process and the stability of the adsorbed layer on the copper surface. In general the magnitude of ΔG°_{ads} approximately is -20 kJ mol^{-1} or lower is assumed for existing electrostatic interaction between inhibitor and charged metal sur-

Fig. 3. Effect of inhibitor on the polarization curve of copper in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 4. Curves fitting of the inhibitors adsorption by Langmuir isotherm.

Table 4. Data from Langmuir isotherm for copper in 0.6 M NaCl containing inhibitors

Inhibitor	K_{ads} ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	R^2	ΔG°_{ads} (kJ mol^{-1})
1	1.25×10^5	0.991	–39.8208
2	5×10^4	0.997	–37.5045
3	2.50×10^5	0.999	–41.573
4	5×10^5	0.999	–43.3252
5	2×10^6	0.999	–46.8297
6	1×10^6	0.999	–45.0774
7	2.50×10^5	0.997	–41.573
8	1×10^6	0.999	–45.0774
9	5×10^6	1.00	–49.146
10	3.33×10^6	1.00	–48.121

face, i.e. physisorption and values of -40 kJ mol^{-1} or higher involve charge sharing or a transfer from the inhibitor molecules to the metal surface to form a coordinate covalent bond, i.e. chemisorptions^{5,6}. The values of $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{ads}}$ are around -40 kJ mol^{-1} (Table 4). This indicates that the adsorption of these inhibitors take place directly by chemisorptions through the donor behavior of hetero

atoms such as N and O containing lone pair in the inhibitor molecules and the acceptor behavior by vacant d-orbitals of metal surface atoms³³ and mixed ligand complex is formed on the surface of copper. The adsorption is increased by the introduction of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SO}_2^-$ group which may be partly due to physisorption. But this needs further investigations.

Inhibition efficiency of various organic inhibitors against corrosion of copper in salt solution is shown here.

Inhibitor	Concentration	Medium	Efficiency (%)
 2-Amino-5-(ethylthio)-1,3,4-thiadiazole ³⁴	$1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$	3% NaCl	90.0
 Bis-(1-benzotriazolylmethylene)-(2,5)-thiadiazolyl-disulphide	$1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$	3% NaCl	87.6
 Benzotriazole ²⁵	$1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$	0.5 M NaCl	26.2
 1-Hydroxybenzotriazole ³⁵	$5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$	3% NaCl	89.3
 Purine ¹¹	$1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$	1 M NaCl	76.0
 Caffeine ³⁶	$1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$	0.5 M KNO_3	60.0

The inhibition efficiency of these compounds varies from 26–90% in 0.5–1 M NaCl/KNO₃ solution with 10⁻²–10⁻³ M inhibitor concentration. The inhibition efficiency of compound 1-benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis(2-imidazolynyl)ethane (**10**) is 87.0% with 10⁻⁵ M inhibitor concentration. Further improvement in the inhibition efficiency may be possible by introducing appropriate group in the benzene ring. It is also active against *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas stutzeri*. Thus 1-benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis-imidazolynylethane is a promising corrosion inhibitor for copper in aqueous sodium chloride solution and may act as antifouling agent.

Conclusion

Aspartic acid derivatives have shown inhibiting properties for corrosion of copper at pH 6 in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution. The inhibition efficiency increases in the following order **1** < **2** < **3** < **4** < **5** < **6** < **7** < **8** < **9** < **10**. The inhibiting property is predominantly due to chemisorption of the inhibitors on copper surface. Significant improvement in the inhibiting property of aspartic acid is observed by introducing C₆H₅-SO₂- group. Further improvement is achieved by converting the two -COOH groups to benzimidazole, 1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine or imidazoline group in stepwise manner. Improvement in the inhibiting property is due to (i) the π -electron contribution of the benzene/heterocyclic ring, (ii) presence of more active adsorption sites and (iii) higher molecular size. Imidazoline derivatives are found to be better corrosion inhibitor for copper.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to the Head, Chemistry Department, NIT Durgapur for Laboratory facilities and to A. Jana and D. Pahari for some assistance.

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